

**Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research (TPPCR) 2022; Special Edition #02: Commentary on
*Shaw et al.***

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Parent

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Abstract:

This TPPCR commentary discusses the 2020 paper by Shaw et al., “‘A confident parent breeds a confident child’: Understanding the experience and needs of parents whose children will transition from paediatric to adult care” published in Journal of Child Health Care.

This commentary is a part of the Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research commentary series. To learn more or to sign up for our monthly newsletter visit: <https://pediatricpalliative.com/research-blog/>

In reading for the recent parent journal club, this article left the biggest impact on me.

As a new parent myself, I felt the frustration and concern in the voices of the parents of this study; that desire to protect my children and the willingness to pause my development to prioritize theirs. I could absolutely commiserate with the parents, as it seemed they did with each other. With each parent's anecdote, though, a lump of guilt slowly began to form in my throat. I knew, as every parent did, that for every frustration I have felt in parenting there is a child that is equally frustrated in being parented.

What was the voice on the other side of these statements trying to assert? Who was peeking through behind the parents' paraphrasing? What did their children say to evoke these statements from the parents in this study and what did the children feel about their parents' responses? How much of these comments were based in concern for the children and how much were simply the captured internal struggle of the parent consolidating their visions for their children? Why were the children's voices left unheard? The role of the parent is dependent on the contextual relationship with their child; when a study mutes the voice of the child it ambiguates the power of the child in this relationship, oversimplifying the conflict faced by parent advocates and uncentering focus from the child patient.

Parenting, as I have learned in my brief 2-and-a-half-year crash course, is a reactionary role. You meet this tiny enigma that is a baby and are told you are responsible for them to meet their presently undefined potential and overcome their unfortold struggles. All this with, usually, no prior experience. So naturally, as parents, we draw on other experiences, on ideas of success and, inevitably, comparison to others and standardized timelines. There are countless more poetic definitions of parenthood and they are not something I aim to summarize here; my point is, becoming a parent is a role birthed from a new relationship between parent and child, two lives that inevitably become enmeshed and informed by the world around them.

As stated, parenting is a reactionary role; it requires the child's voice to contextualize the parent's response. The model used for this study, a discussion group for parents, took parents out of the context of their relationship with their child. This format removed parents' accountability to their nearly adult children, or any chance for the children to make a rebuttal to their parents' comments and, ultimately, removed the ability to discern the real rather than the perceived struggle for either party in the parent-child dynamic. Like the idiom says: "There are two sides to every story; the truth is somewhere in between."

This loss of context strips the child of the power they hold in their life and the weight they deserve to have in the decisions of their future. Within the study, this loss of context removes the struggle parents face in trying to support their children while overcoming their own wants for their children's needs. For example, the comments regarding some children's struggles to marry or have children, these parent concerns fit a very narrow definition of family dynamic and potential life outcomes for a child. Are these truly struggles for the children or are these struggles of ideologies between parent and child?

Outside the study, the apprehension I have as a parent to a medically complex child, who will likely have to strive even more than other children to be heard in many settings, is that this study, like many others aimed at aiding the ecosystem of pediatric patients, placed the child's voice on the peripheries of the conversation. This study empowered the parent's voices that spoke about their children rather than with their children with medical complexities. The children weren't even in the room – parent voices had no

immediate accountability to their children, the patients, and the parents' unchecked voices were published in an authoritative context without opportunity for rebuttal.

This loss of context and ambiguation of the patient's voice can be overcome; we simply need to center their voices. Start with the patient. If the study began by framing the patient and their concerns (or lack thereof) in transition to adulthood and captured the reactions of the parents, context would have been present, power of the patient would have a better chance of being preserved in the study, and this would have given depth to the struggle patients and their parents face in transitioning to adulthood.

This study could go one step further: a great way to normalize some of these results would be to also include non-medically complex young adults. This study analyzes a marginalized group only within themselves, in this case, medically complex children. When we do this, we risk conflating traits or struggles of individuals as symptoms of their marginal identity, rather than traits and struggles indicative of the intersections of life which they find themselves in, young adulthood. Many of the paraphrased comments from children in this paper are not abnormal for young adults. By not comparing this group of children (and their relationship with their parents), with children without medical complexities, we cannot normalize their concerns and fears. For instance, again drawing on the example of the comments regarding some children's struggles with the concept of marriage or having children; gender identity, ideas of marriage or even the idea of having children as a young adult don't strike me as unique to the subjects of this study. This normalization through comparison of two cohorts of young adults, one with medical complexities and one without, has the potential to create much more nuanced commentary.

I am thankful to the Siden Lab for the opportunity to share my insights on this paper, and to you, dear reader, for listening.